

COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS IS A MODERN AND PROMISING BRANCH OF LANGUAGE SCIENCE

Rakhmonkulova M.T.

Fergana State University, PhD student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13956833>

Abstract. *This article is dedicated to the emergence of cognitive linguistics and the study of its main theories of development. It provides detailed information about the history of cognitive linguistics, particularly highlighting George Lakoff's contributions. The main focus of the article is on the connection between cognitive linguistics and human consciousness, demonstrating how theories emerging from this field reflect human thought processes in language.*

Keywords: *cognitive linguistics, communication, cognitive processes, concept, understanding, conceptual world.*

INTRODUCTION

Cognitive linguistics is a modern branch of linguistics that deeply studies the interaction between language and human consciousness. Cognitive linguistics is a theory that examines the relationship between language and thought. This field analyzes language not only from the perspective of grammar and syntax but also in relation to cognitive processes associated with human consciousness such as thinking, memory, and experience. It integrates several disciplines including psychology, neuroscience, and linguistics. Cognitive linguists view language not merely as a collection of alphabets or grammatical rules but as an essential element related to human thought and cognitive processes.

The following key issues are studied in cognitive linguistics:

1. Language and thought: Issues such as how language shapes human thought and how thought shapes language are explored.
2. Language learning: The role of cognitive abilities in the process of acquiring new languages is studied, including how these abilities function during language acquisition.
3. Neurolinguistics: The functioning of the brain while an individual uses a particular language is examined, specifically which neurons are involved in language use.
4. Semantics and meaning: Understanding meanings expressed through language and their cognitive interpretation are investigated.
5. Discourse analysis: The manifestation of cognitive processes during interpersonal communication is analyzed.

Cognitive linguistics studies the relationships between language and cognition, viewing language not only as a means of communication but also as a crucial system that plays an important role in shaping human thought. Notable researchers in this field include George Lakoff and Ronald Langacker, whose work has provided new insights into how language expresses concepts in the human mind. Unlike traditional grammar theories, cognitive linguistics sees language as a dynamic and context-dependent process.

ANALYSIS AND METHODS OF LITERATURE

Cognitive linguistics is a field of study that examines language in relation to cognitive processes. Many scholars have been active in this area. The following scholars have engaged with cognitive linguistics:

1. George Lakoff - Founder of cognitive linguistics, known for his work on "metaphors."
2. Mark Johnson - Co-author with Lakoff of the book "Metaphors We Live By."
3. Ronald Langacker - A scholar who developed cognitive grammar.
4. Eve Sweetser - Conducted research in semantics and the cognitive aspects of language.
5. Gilles Fauconnier - Known for the theory of "mental spaces" in cognitive linguistics.
6. Terry Langendoen - Worked in cognitive linguistics and other areas of linguistics.
7. William Croft - Conducted research on cognitive theories and typology.

In cognitive linguistics, the terms "concept" and "notion" play a crucial role, and there are some differences between them. The term "concept" (from Latin "conceptus," meaning "understood" or "brought to mind") is essential in studying the relationship between language and thought. This term is primarily used to refer to an idea or mental representation that expresses the general characteristics of something or a notion.

Concepts are formed and accepted through cognitive processes in the human brain. They define people's worldviews and are expressed through language. From the perspective of cognitive linguistics, concepts are a significant factor that influences meaning and communication processes.

Concepts can often be expressed visually and semantically. For example, the concept of something might relate to its physical properties (such as color and shape) as well as its social or cultural context. Thus, in cognitive linguistics, the term concept has a broad meaning, providing essential foundations for human learning processes and interactions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the perspective of cognitive linguistics, concepts are regarded as logical structures that exist in human consciousness. They define how individuals perceive, imagine, and express the world through language. Concepts are also shaped by culture and personal experience, making each individual's conceptual world unique.

For example, the concept of "summer" encompasses all the associations related to the summer season (warm weather, relaxation, vacation, etc.). Cognitive linguistics studies issues such as how concepts emerge, their structure, and how initial meanings are expressed. Although the terms "concept" and "notion" are semantically similar, there are certain differences between them. The term "concept" typically expresses a specific idea, thought, or object. Concepts are used by people to understand and classify the world around them. They can be abstract or general; for example, "justice," "beauty," or "life." Concepts can often be interpreted differently in various contexts.

On the other hand, a notion is considered a more precise term that refers to an individual or personal interpretation of a particular concept. A notion is shaped by an individual's experiences, knowledge, and culture. For instance, the notion of "justice" may differ from person to person; one person might understand justice as adherence to laws while another might associate it with values based on humanity.

In cognitive linguistics, although these two terms are interconnected, their meanings and usage differ depending on context.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, cognitive linguistics not only helps to solve language-related problems but also provides a deeper understanding of human thought processes and consciousness. Language is not just a medium of communication; it is also a powerful force that shapes our worldview, emotions, and analytical abilities. Through research in this field, we gain a broader understanding

of cognitive processes and uncover profound connections within the literature and culture of humanity. The examples provided in the article further clarify the distinction between concepts and notions. This allows readers to better grasp the theories of cognitive linguistics. Overall, your article makes an important contribution to illuminating the significance of cognitive linguistics and its impact on the structure of human consciousness. Cognitive linguistics helps us to understand not only language but also human thinking methods more deeply, which plays a crucial role in our social and cultural lives.

REFERENCES

1. Fauconnier, G., & Turner, M. (2002). *The Way We Think: Conceptual Blending and the Mind's Hidden Complexities*. Basic Books.
2. Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors We Live By*. University of Chicago Press.
3. Langacker, R. W. (1987). *Foundations of Cognitive Grammar: Volume 1: Theoretical Prerequisites*. Stanford University Press.
4. Mandler, J. M. (2004). *The Foundations of Mind: Origins of Conceptual Thought*. Oxford University Press.